

**DEVELOPMENT OF RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE
IMPLEMENTATION OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES FOR FIRE SAFETY
OF INDUSTRIAL BUILDINGS**

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we will develop practical methods and concepts for protection against fire disasters that may occur in high-rise buildings, and then study the requirements for new fire protection systems and the main changes it is important to analyze the problems that arise

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada ko'p qavatli binolarda sodir bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan yong'in falokatlaridan himoya qilishning amaliy usullari va tushunchalarini ishlab chiqish, so'ngra yangi yong'indan himoya qilish tizimlariga qo'yiladigan talablarni o'rganish va asosiy o'zgarishlardan kelib chiqadigan muammolarni tahlil qilish muhimdir.

Keywords: Fire protection, security system retrofitting, fire safety, building components, traditional methods, innovative technologies.

Kalit so'zlar: Yong'indan himoya qilish, xavfsizlik tizimini qayta jihozlash, yong'in xavfsizligi, qurilish komponentlari, an'anaviy usullar, innovatsion texnologiyalar.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that today, along with developed countries, the number of high-rise skyscrapers with various complex designs and structures is increasing in the territory of our republic. This, in turn, creates the need to bring the security system of buildings to the level that meets the requirements of the times and to use new methods and technologies in the fire safety system. It is precisely the issues of fire suppression in high-rise buildings that require the complexity of rescue operations, the employees of emergency fire departments to have comprehensive knowledge of the processes and

characteristics of fires in high-rise buildings, high professional skills, physical and psychological preparation. In addition, the use of modern technologies in high-rise buildings, knowledge of fire risk and operational tactical features of buildings allows to eliminate fires with minimal damage, and to take quick measures to save people's lives and health. Currently, the increase in building height regulations, the fact that buildings with a height of more than 80 meters are being actively built in the main cities of Uzbekistan (the highest indicator is currently "NEST ONE" 266.5 meters), high architectural and special design requirements in buildings lead to the construction of non-standard buildings for urban planning. This means that the fire safety system includes modern firefighting systems and collective rescue equipment,

Determines the urgency of the need to use new fire and rescue equipment and tactics for emergency fire departments in the organization of fire extinguishing and rescue operations. Another relevance of the topic shows that the main part of the statistical indicators presented regarding the causes of fires observed throughout the year in the territory of our republic, objects subject to fire and the risk of fire scale are related to high-rise residential buildings.

Fires in high-rise buildings can have fatal consequences due to a number of inconveniences: the use of combustible materials in building structures and interior decoration; automatic fire alarm and fire extinguishing

system malfunctions; the rapid spread of fire vertically and strong smoke in buildings, as well as the presence of openings between floors, ceilings, stairs, and openings leads to inefficient organization of fire extinguishing and rescue operations.

The general principles of the organization of fire extinguishing and rescue operations are defined in a number of documents of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of our Republic.

but these materials do not allow to reliably predict and correctly calculate the possible consequences of fire in modern high-rise buildings. Calculating the consumption of fire protection forces and means, water and other fire-fighting substances necessary for effective fire extinguishing and rescue operations is a matter of modern information technologies.

the fact that the fire protection authorities are not yet effectively introduced to their activities,

Another important aspect is that the level of automation of the management of emergency fire and rescue units remains very low. The purpose of the research is to conduct a structural analysis of the problem of automation of fire extinguishing and rescue operations in high-rise buildings and to develop functional, mathematical and simulation models in the appropriate system shell of new data. By their very nature, high-rise buildings present unusual fire safety challenges. A number of fundamental issues must be addressed to ensure a reasonable level of safety from fire and its effects for designers, builders, operators and owners of these structures.

The building structure should be resistant to fire for a long time. □□The fire and its consequences spread vertically, affecting a large number of building occupants.

Active fire systems may be disconnected from utilities and should be self-contained.

It is very difficult to completely evacuate the building. Only a Protect in Place strategy with selective evacuation from the fire zone is required.

Passengers to be evacuated must stay off the ground and rely on vertical means of escape.

Firefighting operations occur internally and often away from underground sources.

METHODOLOGY In this study, all scientific electronic and written sources on the topic were studied.

State-of-the-art technology in fire safety systems in high-rise buildings, the fire engine called "Drongo" is one of the most unusual units in the PSC fleet. It is used to extinguish complex fires, transport personnel and equipment to the scene of an accident, and illuminate the scene of a fire.

Smoke control-HVAC (heating, ventilation and air conditioning) system or technology that can be controlled by fans and dampers using a special system to control the flow of air through the building in the event of a fire.

State-of-the-art emergency lighting panels such as Emergency Lighting-Lux Intelligent can self-test each luminaire and ensure that it operates when needed. The range of traditional and LED lighting is now vast and ambient lighting can be converted for emergency use, providing compatibility and performance benefits.

For operators of the Bronte Sky fit, this means faster leveling, working lights, light groups and easy control of the cage load, larger displays that look good even in sunlight, easy navigation, chassis information on the screens, built-in help recommendations and quick guides, as well as resistance. There is also a built-in water pump screen with improved pump operation capabilities for the firefighting sector.

RESULT DISCUSSION

Recommendations regarding the introduction of modern technologies for fire safety in multi-story buildings The following special requirements are set for multi-story buildings

Structural fire resistance and passive protection measures Automatic sprinkler systems Standpipes (Damp risers) Occupant and fire department voice communications Unlocking stairways to allow evacuees to re-enter the building below the fire. Many of these regulations have been incorporated into tall buildings around the world.

The fire safety system of modern high-rise buildings must meet the following requirements:

Active and passive fire protection features to control fire growth and reduce the impact of fire on the structure and its occupants.

Active systems include automatic sprinkler protection to control small area fires and smoke control systems to control smoke movement for safe evacuation of occupants. Passive elements include fire barriers to prevent the fire-resistant structure from spreading vertically. All active and passive systems must be maintained throughout the life of the building to ensure they function properly when needed.

Means of egress to facilitate the evacuation of passengers in case of fire.

Occupants of the building must be protected from the effects of the fire in the building when they are evacuated from the fire area. Fire-resistant enclosed and

mechanically pressurized stairs protect occupants from fire and smoke during evacuation. Fire detection, alarm and communication systems should alert building staff of a fire and instruct occupants to evacuate.

Fire support systems primarily support operations from within a building, often far from fire service facilities and ground support. Fire support systems include vehicle access, firefighter lifts (elevators), fire command center, fire hose (wet riser) systems, and firefighter communications. Additionally, construction response plans and procedures should be closely coordinated with first responders. For current technical standards, the process of implementing a successful fire safety approach when designing new high-rise buildings or renovating existing structures is critical. Technical design of high-rise buildings always begins with the creation of a regulatory framework for the project. This is done by approving the local codes and standards that apply to the project – even in areas where there are many high-rise buildings. For many projects, building codes may not fully address fire safety issues, and new requirements need to be set to "improve" the fire and life safety aspects of design.

A full evacuation of a high-rise building is expected to be required anew through a variety of scenarios, including loss of power or loss of mechanical systems. Therefore, elevators can provide an alternative means of evacuating building occupants in certain emergency situations. To achieve this function, elevators must be specially designed for this purpose and provided with emergency power. A building must have safe spaces (e.g. shelter areas, sky lobbies, or enclosed elevator lobbies) to facilitate the placement or evacuation of occupants. Elevators should be included as part of the building's emergency response plan and operated by building personnel trained in emergency situations. Atriums in high-rise buildings such as NEST ONO in Tashkent create a new complication in the evacuation of passengers.

High-rise fire safety strategies rely heavily on active fire systems and complex evacuation sequences. Therefore, operational aspects of high-rise buildings are important. Active fire systems must be continuously monitored, maintained and tested to ensure their reliability in emergency situations. Another important operational aspect is emergency planning and training. This begins with an Emergency Management Plan

that outlines all foreseeable emergency scenarios and the building staff's response to those emergencies. An emergency management plan should address all threats, whether natural disasters, terrorism, and security or systemic emergencies. They should include pre-planned response procedures for each incident and should include staff training and drills.

Future directions for high-rise fire safety

In the future, for the design and operation of high-rise fire safety, a number of increasingly complex active fire systems for fire control, smoke control, evacuation and fire extinguishing, building fire resistance and strength, ensuring the stability of buildings, and the reliability of important construction features will be more important than all the requirements.

CONCLUSION

Based on this article, it consists of a systematic analysis of the problem of automation of fire extinguishing and rescue operations in multi-story buildings and the development of functional, mathematical and simulation models in the appropriate system shell of new data. Recommendations for achieving the development of scientific and methodological apparatus based on new information technologies for increasing the efficiency of fire extinguishing and rescue work in buildings were considered. In the research presented in the article: A structural analysis of the problem of automation of fire extinguishing and rescue operations in multi-story buildings was carried out. the development of mathematical models of traffic control processes was studied. literature was analyzed on the development of a method for supporting management decisions in the organization of fire extinguishing in multi-story buildings using CALS technologies. The obtained results can be the basis for prospective regulatory documents regulating the procedure for creating fire safety information systems for multi-story buildings.

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